

INFLUENCE OF MASTER TEACHERS' INSTRUCTIONAL LEADERSHIP ON TEACHER DEVELOPMENT IN MAITUM 1 AND KIAMBA 1 DISTRICTS: A CONVERGENT PARALLEL MIXED-METHODS STUDY

Rhea Mae C. Dubal ¹, Emie Rose C. Gacal ¹, Jennalyn Sato-Sison, PhD ²,
Norman M. Norberte, PhD ²

¹College of Education, Mindanao State University-General Santos City, Philippines

²Department of Education, General Santos City, Philippines

ABSTRACT

Master Teachers, positioned at the Highly Proficient level of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST), play a vital role in strengthening instructional quality and supporting teacher growth. This study examined the influence of Master Teachers' instructional leadership skills on teacher development in Maitum 1 and Kiamba 1 Districts, Sarangani Province, using a convergent parallel mixed-methods design. Quantitative data analyzed through descriptive statistics and Spearman's rho revealed that instructional leadership skills were highly demonstrated ($M = 3.26$) and teacher development was strongly impacted ($M = 3.42$), with a highly significant positive relationship between the variables ($r = 0.798$, $p < .001$). Qualitative findings complemented these results by describing Master Teachers as mentors, instructional guides, curriculum facilitators, and role models who foster teacher growth through feedback, coaching, collaboration, and reflection. The integration of findings showed strong convergence, confirming that effective instructional leadership enhances teachers' competence, confidence, motivation, and professional engagement, while highlighting the need to further strengthen differentiated instruction, technology integration, instructional innovation, and structured support for newly hired teachers.

Keywords: *instructional leadership, Master Teachers, teacher development, mentoring and coaching, monitoring and evaluation, mixed methods research.*

INTRODUCTION

Master Teachers in the Department of Education are recognized as highly competent educators who possess advanced knowledge and expertise in curriculum and instruction. Because of their experience and professional competence, they are often referred to as teachers of teachers since they guide, mentor, and support fellow teachers in improving classroom instruction and professional practice (Hare, 2024). Their role goes beyond regular classroom teaching because they are also expected to assist school heads in instructional supervision and in strengthening the overall teaching and learning process within schools.

In addition, the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers recognize the important role of Master Teachers in promoting teacher competence and improving classroom effectiveness. These policies show that instructional leadership should not only come from school heads but should also be shared with experienced teachers who can contribute to instructional improvement.

Several studies have shown that distributed instructional leadership positively affects teacher growth and school improvement. When leadership responsibilities are shared, teachers receive stronger support through mentoring, supervision, collaboration, and professional guidance. International study by Bush and Anania (2023) emphasized that instructional leadership, in terms of developing a positive learning climate, directly and positively affects teacher efficacy. In the Philippine setting, related studies also support the importance of Master Teachers' instructional leadership in teacher development. Cadacio and Albite (2025) found that instructional leadership and teaching competencies were strongly related to teacher development. Similarly, studies conducted by Tagacay et al. (2025), Quisquino (2022), Oliva and Bautista (2025), and Orbe and Manooos-Pacia (2025) found that the instructional leadership competencies of Master Teachers were significantly associated with improved teacher performance. These findings indicated that Master Teachers play an important role in helping teachers improve classroom instruction through mentoring, technical assistance, and continuous support.

However, not all studies reported consistent results regarding the effects of instructional leadership. Federico and Francisco (2024) as well as Reyes and Opra (2025) presented opposing findings, revealing no significant relationship between master teachers' leadership skills and teacher performance. This suggested that leadership alone may not automatically translate into measurable improvements in performance, especially when institutional support systems, structured interventions, or sustained monitoring mechanisms are insufficient. Because of these differences in findings, further studies are needed to better understand how instructional leadership influences teacher development in different school contexts.

Although many studies have examined instructional leadership, most of them focused mainly on school heads or on general leadership practices. Limited attention has been given to the specific role of Master Teachers as instructional leaders and their direct influence on the professional development of teachers, particularly in rural public secondary schools. This gap is evident in the Maitum and Kiamba Districts in the Division

of Sarangani, where schools continue to face challenges related to post-pandemic recovery, increasing teacher workloads, and limited educational resources.

Considering these gaps, the present study was conducted to examine the influence of Master Teachers' instructional leadership on teacher development in public secondary schools in the Maitum and Kiamba Districts, Division of Sarangani. Specifically, the study aimed to determine how the instructional leadership practices of Master Teachers contribute to teachers' professional growth, instructional practices, motivation, and overall performance. Using a convergent parallel mixed-methods design, the study combined quantitative data on instructional leadership and teacher development with qualitative insights from teachers lived experiences. Through this approach, the researchers hoped to provide a clearer understanding of the role of Master Teachers in instructional leadership and to offer recommendations that may help improve leadership practices and teaching quality in the division.

Research Questions

This study seeks to determine the influence of master teachers' instructional leadership on teacher development in selected public secondary schools in Kiamba 1 and Maitum 1 Districts using a Convergent Parallel Mixed-Methods Design. Specifically, this study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of age; sex; highest educational attainment; years in teaching and; current position?
2. What is the level of instructional leadership skills of master teachers in terms of: monitoring and evaluation; curriculum enhancement; modeling effective practices; mentorship and coaching; and personal growth and professional development?
3. What is the impact of master teachers' instructional leadership on teacher development in terms of: teacher performance; professional growth; instructional practices; and teacher motivation and engagement?
4. Is there a significant relationship between master teachers' instructional leadership and teacher development?
5. How do teachers describe their experiences with Master Teachers' instructional leadership?
6. What perceived influences do Master Teachers have on teachers' development?
7. What challenges and supports shape teachers' development under Master Teachers' leadership?
8. How are the quantitative and qualitative findings similar or different in portraying the influence of instructional leadership on teacher development?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a convergent parallel mixed-methods research design to examine the influence of Master Teachers' instructional leadership on teacher development in public secondary schools in Kiamba I and Maitum I Districts, Division of Sarangani. The quantitative and qualitative strands were conducted simultaneously, analyzed separately, and integrated during interpretation.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in selected public secondary schools in Kiamba I and Maitum I Districts, Division of Sarangani.

Research Respondents & Sampling Technique

The quantitative respondents consisted of 52 public secondary school teachers selected from a population of 214 teachers using a 90% confidence level and 10% margin of error. For the qualitative strand, 10 teacher-participants were selected through purposive sampling based on established inclusion criteria, including including at least one year of teaching experience and exposure to Classroom Observation (COT) or Technical Assistance conducted by a Master Teacher within the past 12 months, and must be assigned in the identified schools in Kiamba I or Maitum I, who holds a Teacher I-III position.

Data Gathering Procedure

Quantitative data were collected through Google Forms, while qualitative data were gathered through face-to-face Key Informant Interviews (KII) and were conducted in private settings, audio-recorded with consent, and transcribed for thematic analysis. Ethical considerations such as confidentiality, anonymity, informed consent, and voluntary participation were strictly observed.

Research Instruments

The first section of the questionnaire collected demographic data from the teacher respondents, including their age, sex, length of teaching service, highest educational attainment, and designation. The second section of the questionnaire assessed the instructional leadership skills of Master Teachers, adapted from Federico et al. (2024) and Cadacio & Albite (2025). It consisted of 10 indicators focusing on the key areas of instructional leadership: monitoring and evaluation, curriculum enhancement (Federico et al., 2024), modeling effective practices, mentorship and coaching, and professional growth and development (Cadacio & Albite 2025). The third section of the questionnaire explored teacher development, focusing on Teacher Performance; Professional Growth; Instructional Practices; and Teacher Motivation and Engagement. Responses were rated

using a four-point Likert scale: 4 (Strongly Agree), 3 (Agree), 2 (Disagree), and 1 (Strongly Disagree). On the other hand, a semi-structured interview guide was also employed for the qualitative component.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics and Spearman's rho correlation were used to analyze quantitative data since the data were derived from ordinal Likert-scale responses and did not meet the assumptions of normal distribution. Thematic analysis was utilized for qualitative data. Findings from both strands were integrated during interpretation.

Scope and Delimitation

This study examined the influence of Master Teachers' instructional leadership on teacher development in terms of monitoring and evaluation, curriculum enhancement, modeling effective practices, mentorship and coaching, and professional growth and development. Teacher development was assessed in relation to teacher performance, professional growth, instructional practices, and teacher motivation and engagement. The study was geographically delimited to selected public secondary schools in Kiamba I and Maitum I Districts, Schools Division of Sarangani, during the School Year 2025-2026. Respondents were limited to secondary school teachers assigned in the identified schools. Master Teachers, non-teaching personnel, and elementary school teachers were excluded.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Demographic Profile of Respondents N=52

Indicators	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
20-25 years old	3	5.78
26-30 years old	20	38.46
31-35 years old	11	21.15
36-40 years old	8	15.38
41-50 years old	10	19.23
51-55 years old	0	0
56-65 years old	0	0
Sex		
Female	33	63.46
Male	19	36.54
Highest Educational Attainment		
Bachelor's Degree	18	34.62
Bachelor's Degree with Units in Master's Program	28	53.84
Master's Degree	2	3.84
Master's Degree with Units in Doctoral Program	4	7.70
Doctoral Degree	0	0
Years in Teaching		

Below 5 Years	25	48.08
6-10 Years	19	36.54
11-15 Years	6	11.54
16-20 Years	0	0
21 Years- Above	2	3.84
Current Position		
Teacher 1	22	42.31
Teacher 2	19	36.54
Teacher 3	11	21.15

The demographic profile of the respondents showed that the majority belong to the early to mid-adult age range, with most teachers aged 26-30 years old (38.46%), followed by 31-35 years old (21.15%) and 41-50 years old (19.23%). Only a small proportion were 20-25 years old (5.78%), while no respondents were above 50 years old. This suggests a relatively young teaching workforce in the selected districts. In terms of sex distribution, female teachers dominated the sample (63.46%), while males comprised 36.54%, indicating a common gender pattern in the teaching profession where females are more represented.

Regarding educational attainment, most respondents held a Bachelor's Degree with units in a Master's program (53.84%), followed by those with a completed Bachelor's Degree (34.62%). Only a few had completed a Master's Degree (3.84%) or were pursuing doctoral units (7.70%), and none had completed a doctorate. This indicates that while teachers are generally qualified, many are still in the process of advancing their graduate studies.

For years in teaching, almost half of the respondents had less than 5 years of experience (48.08%), followed by 6-10 years (36.54%). Only a small percentage had more than 10 years of service, indicating that most respondents are relatively early in their professional careers. This aligns with the age distribution, reflecting a young and developing teaching workforce.

In terms of current position, the majority were Teacher I (42.31%), followed by Teacher II (36.54%) and Teacher III (21.15%). This suggests that most participants are classroom teachers who are still in the early stages of their professional progression.

Overall, the findings indicated that the respondents are predominantly young, early-career, female teachers with limited but developing professional experience. This profile is important in interpreting the study's findings, as early-career teachers may be more reliant on Master Teachers' instructional leadership for mentoring, guidance, and professional development.

Table 2.1. Level of Instructional Leadership Skills of Master Teachers in Terms of Monitoring & Evaluation

Indicative Statements <i>The Master Teacher ...</i>	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. holds meetings and discuss ratees issues regularly.	3.33	Highly Demonstrated	4
2. assists in evaluating the performance of teachers.	3.48	Highly Demonstrated	1
3. leads to discuss critical school issues and reminds teachers of key rule-outs and deliverables for compliance.	3.35	Highly Demonstrated	3
4. provides timely, accurate and specific feedback in collegial manner to teachers regarding performance.	3.37	Highly Demonstrated	2
5. conducts FGDs with teachers regularly to assess learners' progress.	3.13	Demonstrated	9
6. constantly monitors teachers' teaching needs.	3.19	Demonstrated	8
7. provides feedback to School Head on teachers' & learners' needs.	3.29	Highly Demonstrated	5.5
8. assesses overall academic implementation to know where to help.	3.29	Highly Demonstrated	5.5
9. determines the classroom needs of teachers.	3.25	Demonstrated	7
	Overall Mean 3.30	Highly Demonstrated	
<i>Legend: 1.00-1.74=Not Demonstrated</i>		<i>2.50-3.24= Demonstrated</i>	
<i>1.75-2.49=Partially Demonstrated</i>		<i>3.25-4.00= Highly Demonstrated</i>	

Table 2.1 revealed that the instructional leadership skills of Master Teachers in terms of monitoring and evaluation were Highly Demonstrated, as reflected by the overall mean of 3.30, indicating strong engagement in supervisory and evaluative functions that support instructional improvement.

The strongest indicator is *assisting in evaluating the performance of teachers* (Mean = 3.48, Rank 1), showing that Master Teachers are highly involved in formal teacher evaluation and instructional supervision. This suggests their active role in ensuring teaching quality through structured assessment and professional guidance. This aligns with Cadacio & Albite (2024), who emphasized that monitoring and evaluation serve as structured mechanisms for improving instructional practices and identifying development needs. Meanwhile, the lowest-rated indicator is *conducting FGDs with teachers to assess learners' progress* (Mean = 3.13, Rank 9), though still interpreted as *Demonstrated*. This indicates that while collaborative monitoring practices exist, they are less frequently implemented compared to individualized supervision and feedback mechanisms. Ministry of General Education (2018) supports this by emphasizing that monitoring and evaluation should be continuous and collaborative to ensure effective instructional implementation.

2.2. Level of Instructional Leadership Skills of Master Teachers in Terms of Curriculum Enhancement

Indicative Statements <i>The Master Teacher ...</i>	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. works closely with teachers in discussing curriculum to enhance teaching competencies.	3.29	Highly Demonstrated	2
2. leads in the preparation of learning materials, localizing and in contextualizing the curriculum.	3.15	Demonstrated	8.5
3. helps implement the measures by the school to enhance teaching-learning experiences.	3.25	Highly Demonstrated	4
4. coordinates programs that enhances the delivery of curriculum content.	3.27	Highly Demonstrated	3
5. discusses curriculum goals in relation with teaching strategies with new teachers.	3.35	Highly Demonstrated	1
6. develops strategies that will help foster teaching and learning.	3.21	Demonstrated	6
7. trains newly hired teachers with effective teaching skills.	3.08	Demonstrated	10
8. interprets salient curriculum areas to ensure that teachers are enlightened.	3.17	Demonstrated	7
9. initiates group activities that intend to evaluate curriculum content to achieve academic goals.	3.15	Demonstrated	8.5
10. helps track teachers' teaching skills to ensure that each one is aligned in using effective strategies.	3.23	Demonstrated	5
	Overall Mean 3.22	Demonstrated	
<i>Legend: 1.00-1.74=Not Demonstrated</i>		<i>2.50-3.24= Demonstrated</i>	
<i>1.75-2.49=Partially Demonstrated</i>		<i>3.25-4.00= Highly Demonstrated</i>	

Table 2.2 presented the level of instructional leadership skills of Master Teachers in terms of curriculum enhancement, with an overall mean of 3.22 verbally interpreted as Demonstrated. Their most significant skill is their ability to discuss curriculum goals in relation to teaching strategies with new teachers (Mean = 3.35, Rank 1), indicating strong guidance in aligning instructional planning with curriculum standards. This reflects their role in providing direction and clarity to novice teachers, consistent with Ma and Marion (2021), who emphasized curriculum alignment as a collaborative and continuous instructional process. Likewise, Özdemir et al. (2018) highlighted that curriculum enhancement is strengthened through structured guidance and shared understanding of learning goals. In contrast, the lowest-rated indicator is training newly hired teachers with effective teaching skills (Mean = 3.08, Rank 10), interpreted as *Demonstrated*. This suggests that while mentoring and curriculum support are evident, structured induction and formal training practices are less consistently implemented. Similarly, indicators such

as leading the preparation of localized and contextualized learning materials (Mean = 3.15, Rank 8.5) also reflect areas needing strengthening, particularly in curriculum adaptation and instructional innovation, as noted by Lee et al. (2012).

In synthesis, the results implied that while Master Teachers demonstrate strong collaborative and coordination skills in curriculum enhancement, there remains a need to further strengthen structured training, contextualization, and curriculum innovation practices. This would ensure a more balanced leadership approach that integrates both instructional alignment and capacity-building functions.

2.3. Level of Instructional Leadership Skills of Master Teachers in Terms of Modeling of Effective Practices

Indicative Statements <i>The Master Teacher ...</i>	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. demonstrates exemplary teaching through consistent application of research-backed instructional strategies in my daily lessons	3.19	Demonstrated	4.5
2. actively showcases effective classroom management techniques, creating a positive, engaging, and productive learning environment that serves as a model for colleagues.	3.17	Demonstrated	7
3. models the skillful integration of technology to enhance teaching and learning, demonstrating innovative and purposeful uses of digital tools.	3.13	Demonstrated	9.5
4. articulates the rationale behind my instructional choices, making pedagogical thinking visible and accessible to other educators through explanations and reflections	3.19	Demonstrated	4.5
5. provides first-hand examples of effective teaching in action, allowing colleagues to observe and learn in real-time.	3.13	Demonstrated	9.5
6. models effective assessment practices, utilizing a variety of formative and summative strategies to accurately gauge student understanding and inform instruction.	3.15	Demonstrated	8
7. engages in continuous self-reflection and professional learning, staying current with educational research and trends, and demonstrating a commitment to ongoing improvement.	3.19	Demonstrated	4.5
8. collaboratively plans and shares resources, model effective teamwork in the development of high-quality instructional materials.	3.25	Highly Demonstrated	2
9. demonstrates effective communication and collaboration with students, parents, and colleagues, fostering a supportive and communicative learning community.	3.31	Highly Demonstrated	1
10. models the effective differentiation of instruction to meet the diverse learning needs of all students, showcasing strategies for providing equitable access and support.	3.19	Demonstrated	4.5
Overall Mean	3.19	Demonstrated	

Legend: 1.00-1.74=Not Demonstrated
 1.75-2.49=Partially Demonstrated

2.50-3.24= Demonstrated
 3.25-4.00= Highly Demonstrated

Table 2.3 revealed the level of instructional leadership skills of Master Teachers in terms of modeling effective practices, with an overall mean of 3.19 verbally interpreted as Demonstrated. The strongest skill is their ability to demonstrate effective communication and collaboration with students, parents, and colleagues (Mean = 3.31, Rank 1), indicating strong interpersonal engagement and the establishment of a supportive learning community.

On the other hand, the lowest-rated indicators are skillful integration of technology in teaching (Mean = 3.13, Rank 9.5) and providing first-hand examples of effective teaching in action (Mean = 3.13, Rank 9.5), both interpreted as Demonstrated. This implies that while Master Teachers exhibit modeling behaviors, structured demonstration practices-particularly in technology integration and live teaching exemplars-are less consistently observed. Similarly, modeling effective assessment practices (Mean = 3.15, Rank 8) reflects moderate implementation, suggesting room for strengthening in assessment demonstration and instructional visibility. Overall, the findings indicated that while Master Teachers demonstrate strong collaborative and communicative modeling practices, the variation in indicator scores suggested limited consistency in highly visible instructional modeling such as technology integration, demonstration teaching, and assessment modeling.

2.4. Level of Instructional Leadership Skills of Master Teachers in Terms of Mentorship and Coaching

Indicative Statements <i>The Master Teacher ...</i>	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. establishes trusting and supportive relationships with mentees, creating a safe space for open dialogue, reflection, and professional growth.	3.44	Highly Demonstrated	1.5
2. proactively offers guidance and support to colleagues, sharing their expertise and insights to help them refine their teaching practices and achieve their professional goals.	3.37	Highly Demonstrated	4
3. leads focused group discussions (FGDs) to explore critical school issues, guiding teachers in reflective dialogue and collaborative solution-finding.	3.31	Highly Demonstrated	7
4. proactively reminds teachers of important rules and deliverables, ensuring a supportive structure for compliance and effective practice.	3.35	Highly Demonstrated	5
5. offers timely, accurate, and specific feedback to teachers in a collegial manner, promoting self-reflection and continuous improvement in their performance.	3.27	Highly Demonstrated	8.5

6. models effective coaching techniques, including active listening, asking powerful questions, and providing constructive feedback that encourages self-reflection and action planning.	3.44	Highly Demonstrated	1.5
7. continuously monitors and identifies teachers' professional development needs, allowing for tailored mentoring and coaching support.	3.38	Highly Demonstrated	3
8. provides specific and actionable insights into a mentee's practice, focusing on areas for growth and celebrating successes.	3.33	Highly Demonstrated	6
9. shares resources and best practices relevant to a mentee's needs and context, connecting them with valuable professional development opportunities.	3.25	Highly Demonstrated	10
10. models continuous learning and reflection inspires mentees to embrace a growth mindset and engage in ongoing professional development.	3.27	Highly Demonstrated	8.5
	Overall Mean	3.34	Highly Demonstrated
<i>Legend: 1.00-1.74=Not Demonstrated</i>		<i>2.50-3.24= Demonstrated</i>	
<i>1.75-2.49=Partially Demonstrated</i>		<i>3.25-4.00= Highly Demonstrated</i>	

Table 2.4 indicated the level of instructional leadership skills of Master Teachers in terms of mentorship and coaching, with an overall mean of 3.34 verbally interpreted as Highly Demonstrated. At the outset, the result indicated that Master Teachers consistently demonstrate strong mentoring and coaching practices through guidance, feedback, instructional support, and professional relationship-building with teachers. This suggests that mentorship functions are regularly integrated into their instructional leadership roles.

The highest-rated skills are their ability to establish trusting and supportive relationships with mentees and to model effective coaching techniques (Mean = 3.44, Rank 1.5), indicating strong emphasis on relational trust, psychological safety, and effective coaching behaviors such as active listening, reflective questioning, and constructive feedback. In contrast, the lowest-rated indicator is offering timely, accurate, and specific feedback in a collegial manner (Mean = 3.27, Rank 8.5), although still interpreted as Highly Demonstrated. This suggests that while feedback practices are present, their consistency and specificity may still be improved. Similarly, resource sharing and linking teachers to professional development opportunities (Mean = 3.25, Rank 10) indicated relatively weaker implementation compared to relational mentoring functions. In general, the findings suggested that Master Teachers demonstrate strong mentorship and coaching primarily through trust-building, guidance, and individualized support. However, variation in scores indicated a need to further strengthen structured feedback systems and formal coaching processes. The findings align with Acera (2024), who emphasized that mentorship is a structured professional relationship that involves instructional guidance such as lesson planning, material development, and teaching support to improve classroom practice.

2.5. Level of Instructional Leadership Skills of Master Teachers in Terms of Personal Growth and Professional Development

Indicative Statements <i>The Master Teacher ...</i>	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. engages in professional learning communities and networks, collaborating with other educators to share ideas, resources, and innovative strategies.	3.33	Highly Demonstrated	2
2. demonstrates resilience and adaptability, viewing challenges as opportunities for learning and growth within the dynamic educational landscape.	3.19	Demonstrated	9.5
3. pursues leadership opportunities within and beyond the school, contributing to the profession through mentorship, presentations, and other forms of professional sharing.	3.33	Highly Demonstrated	2
4. develops and maintain a professional portfolio that showcases my growth, accomplishments, and impact on student learning over time.	3.27	Highly Demonstrated	7
5. collaborates with colleagues on action research or other professional inquiry projects to investigate and address specific school or classroom challenges, contributing to the collective knowledge of the faculty.	3.29	Highly Demonstrated	5
6. actively seeks out and participate in professional development opportunities beyond the school level, such as workshops, conferences, and advanced studies, to broaden their perspectives and expertise.	3.29	Highly Demonstrated	5
7. contributes to the development and implementation of school-based professional development programs, sharing their expertise and facilitating learning opportunities for their peer.	3.33	Highly Demonstrated	2
8. stays abreast of current educational trends, research findings, and policy changes, and they consider their implications for their practice and the wider school context.	3.19	Demonstrated	9.5
9. builds professional networks and engages in collaborative partnerships with educators within and beyond their school to exchange ideas, resources, and best practices.	3.25	Highly Demonstrated	8
10. documents and share their professional growth and development experiences, serving as a resource and inspiration for other teachers and contributing to a culture of continuous improvement within the profession.	3.29	Highly Demonstrated	5
	Overall Mean	3.28	Highly Demonstrated
<i>Legend: 1.00-1.74=Not Demonstrated</i>		<i>2.50-3.24= Demonstrated</i>	
<i>1.75-2.49=Partially Demonstrated</i>		<i>3.25-4.00= Highly Demonstrated</i>	

Table 2.5 showed the level of instructional leadership skills of Master Teachers in terms of personal growth and professional development, with an overall mean of 3.28 verbally interpreted as Highly Demonstrated. The result indicates that Master Teachers

consistently engage in continuous learning, leadership development, and professional collaboration. This suggests that personal and professional growth are embedded in their instructional leadership practices through active participation in learning communities, leadership roles, and development initiatives. In terms of the highest-rated indicators, the ability to engage in professional learning communities and networks, pursue leadership opportunities within and beyond the school, and contributes to school-based professional development programs, all obtained a mean of 3.33 and were interpreted as Highly Demonstrated. This implies strong involvement in collaborative learning, leadership extension, and peer professional support. By contrast, the lowest-rated indicators are the ability to demonstrates resilience and adaptability and stay abreast of current educational trends and policy changes, both obtained a mean of 3.19 and were interpreted as Demonstrated. This suggests that while adaptability and awareness of innovations are present, these aspects are less emphasized compared to structured professional development activities and collaborative growth practices.

In relation to the reviewed literature, the findings align with Cadacio and Albite (2024), which emphasized that personal growth through reflection, self-awareness, and emotional intelligence strengthens instructional leadership, mentoring capacity, and professional relationships. In general, the findings revealed that Master Teachers demonstrated strong engagement in personal and professional development through collaboration, leadership participation, and continuous learning, while adaptability and responsiveness to emerging trends may require further strengthening.

Overall Implication

2.6. Summary of Level of Instructional Leadership Skills of Master Teachers

In terms of:	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
2.1. Monitoring & Evaluation	3.30	Highly Demonstrated	2
2.2. Curriculum Enhancement	3.22	Demonstrated	4
2.3. Modeling of Effective Practices	3.19	Demonstrated	5
2.4. Mentorship & Coaching	3.34	Highly Demonstrated	1
2.5. Professional Growth and Professional Development	3.28	Highly Demonstrated	3
	Overall Mean	3.26	Highly Demonstrated
<i>Legend: 1.00-1.74=Not Demonstrated</i>		<i>2.50-3.24= Demonstrated</i>	
<i>1.75-2.49=Partially Demonstrated</i>		<i>3.25-4.00= Highly Demonstrated</i>	

Master Teachers consistently demonstrate strong instructional leadership skills across all five domains, with particularly high performance in mentorship and coaching and monitoring and evaluation, followed by personal and professional development. This suggests that their leadership is most evident in providing guidance, supervision, and continuous professional support to teachers. However, results also revealed variations across indicators, particularly in modeling of effective practices, curriculum enhancement

training support, and aspects of adaptability and responsiveness to emerging trends, which were comparatively lower than other domains.

Table 3.1. Impact of Master Teachers’ Instructional Leadership on Teacher Development in Terms of Teacher Performance

Indicative Statements <i>The Master Teacher’s...</i>	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. guidance has improved my lesson planning.	3.46	Strongly Impacted	1.5
2. feedback has enhanced my classroom management.	3.44	Strongly Impacted	3
3. support has increased my teaching effectiveness.	3.46	Strongly Impacted	1.5
4. mentorship helps me meet performance standards.	3.42	Strongly Impacted	4.5
5. teaching strategies help me improve my student engagement.	3.37	Strongly Impacted	8.5
6. leadership improves my instructional delivery.	3.38	Strongly Impacted	6
7. coaching enables me to handle classroom challenges effectively.	3.37	Strongly Impacted	8.5
8. guidance helps me assess student learning outcomes more accurately.	3.37	Strongly Impacted	8.5
9. support ensures I follow the PPST teaching standards.	3.37	Strongly Impacted	8.5
10. influence enhances my overall teaching performance.	3.42	Strongly Impacted	4.5
	Overall Mean 3.41	Strongly Impacted	
<i>Legend: 1.00-1.74=No Impact</i>	<i>2.50-3.24= Impacted</i>		
<i>1.75-2.49=Slightly Impacted</i>	<i>3.25-4.00= Strongly Impacted</i>		

Table 3.1 showed the impact of Master Teachers’ instructional leadership on teacher development in terms of teacher performance, with an overall mean of 3.41 verbally interpreted as Strongly Impacted. This indicates that teachers perceive Master Teachers’ guidance, feedback, coaching, and support as highly influential in enhancing various aspects of their instructional performance.

In particular, the indicators “guidance has improved my lesson planning” (M=3.46) and “support has increased my teaching effectiveness” (M=3.46) obtained the highest mean scores, both ranked 1.5 and interpreted as Strongly Impacted. This suggests that consistent instructional guidance and professional support play a central role in strengthening teachers’ planning skills and overall teaching effectiveness. On the other hand, several indicators such as student engagement improvement, instructional delivery, classroom challenge management, assessment accuracy, and adherence to PPST standards (M=3.37–3.38) were still interpreted as Strongly Impacted but ranked lower. This implies that while Master Teachers’ influence is consistently positive across all areas, its strongest effect is more evident in foundational instructional tasks such as planning and teaching effectiveness rather than in all dimensions equally.

In relation to the reviewed literature, the findings are consistent with Tagacay et al. (2025) and Quisquino (2022), who emphasized that Master Teachers enhance teacher performance through coaching, mentoring, supervision, and instructional support, leading to improved classroom delivery, planning, and pedagogical competence. In synthesis, the results indicated that Master Teachers’ instructional leadership strongly impacts teacher performance, particularly in lesson planning, teaching effectiveness, and classroom management, while maintaining a consistently positive influence across other instructional domains.

Table 3.2. Impact of Master Teachers’ Instructional Leadership on Teacher Development in Terms of Professional Growth

Indicative Statements <i>The Master Teacher ...</i>	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. encourages me to participate in professional development activities.	3.44	Strongly Impacted	3
2. helps me set professional goals aligned with PPST.	3.48	Strongly Impacted	1
3. provides mentorship that enhances my career progression.	3.40	Strongly Impacted	8
4. contributes to my skills improvement.	3.42	Strongly Impacted	5.5
5. motivates me to learn new teaching strategies.	3.38	Strongly Impacted	9.5
6. encourages participation in school improvement initiatives.	3.42	Strongly Impacted	5.5
7. inspires engagement in collaborative learning activities.	3.42	Strongly Impacted	5.5
8. supports me in pursuing additional certifications or degrees.	3.42	Strongly Impacted	5.5
9. encourages me to think critically about my own teaching practices, decisions, and growth as a professional	3.38	Strongly Impacted	9.5
10. influences my growth in confidence and competence as a teacher.	3.46	Strongly Impacted	2
	Overall Mean	3.43	Strongly Impacted
<i>Legend: 1.00-1.74=No Impact</i>		<i>2.50-3.24= Impacted</i>	
<i>1.75-2.49=Slightly Impacted</i>		<i>3.25-4.00= Strongly Impacted</i>	

Table 3.2 displayed the impact of Master Teachers’ instructional leadership on teacher development in terms of professional growth, with an overall mean of 3.43 verbally interpreted as Strongly Impacted. This indicates that Master Teachers significantly contribute to teachers’ continuous professional development through goal setting, mentoring, motivation, and engagement in learning opportunities. Primarily, the indicator “helps me set professional goals aligned with PPST” obtained the highest mean of 3.48 and ranked first, suggesting that Master Teachers play a crucial role in directing

teachers toward standards-based professional growth. Meanwhile, mentorship for career progression (M=3.40), motivation to learn new strategies (M=3.38), and critical reflection on teaching practices (M=3.38) also reflected strong impact, albeit at comparatively lower ranks, suggesting that deeper reflective and long-term developmental aspects are less emphasized than goal setting and participation-driven growth.

In conclusion, the results indicated that Master Teachers' instructional leadership strongly impacts teachers' professional growth, particularly in goal setting, confidence building, and participation in professional development activities, while also supporting broader aspects of continuous learning and career advancement.

Table 3.3. Impact of Master Teachers' Instructional Leadership on Teacher Development in Terms of Instructional Practices

Indicative Statements <i>The Master Teacher ...</i>	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. helps me apply innovative teaching methods through her guidance.	3.35	Strongly Impacted	9
2. encourages the use of effective assessment strategies.	3.37	Strongly Impacted	8
3. supports the integration of technology in instruction.	3.40	Strongly Impacted	4.5
4. influences my planning for differentiated instruction.	3.29	Strongly Impacted	10
5. helps me improve lesson delivery and student engagement.	3.40	Strongly Impacted	4.5
6. encourages collaborative teaching approaches.	3.42	Strongly Impacted	3
7. guides the adaptation of lessons to student needs.	3.38	Strongly Impacted	6.5
8. provides strategies to align lessons with curriculum standards.	3.44	Strongly Impacted	2
9. models effective instructional practices that I adopt.	3.38	Strongly Impacted	6.5
10. improves the quality of my instructional planning through her mentorship.	3.46	Strongly Impacted	1
	Overall Mean	3.39	Strongly Impacted
<i>Legend: 1.00-1.74=No Impact</i>		<i>2.50-3.24= Impacted</i>	
<i>1.75-2.49=Slightly Impacted</i>		<i>3.25-4.00= Strongly Impacted</i>	

Table 3.3 illustrated the impact of Master Teachers' instructional leadership on teacher development in terms of instructional practices, with an overall mean of 3.39 verbally interpreted as Strongly Impacted. This suggests that Master Teachers significantly contribute to the enhancement of classroom instruction through mentoring, guidance, collaboration, and instructional support. To highlight the results, the indicator "improves the quality of my instructional planning through her mentorship" obtained the highest mean of 3.46 and ranked first, indicating a strong influence of Master Teachers on lesson planning quality. By comparison, application of innovative teaching methods (M=3.35) and planning for differentiated instruction (M=3.29) obtained the lowest

rankings, suggesting that while these practices are supported, they are less prominently developed compared to planning and curriculum alignment.

Findings align with Mendoza and Bautista (2022) who highlighted that master teachers enhance curriculum implementation, pedagogy, and assessment practices, resulting in improved instructional competence. In essence, the results indicated that Master Teachers’ instructional leadership strongly impacts instructional practices, particularly in instructional planning, curriculum alignment, and collaborative teaching, while areas such as innovation and differentiation may still require further enhancement.

Table 3.4. Impact of Master Teachers’ Instructional Leadership on Teacher Development in Terms of Teacher Motivation & Engagement

Indicative Statements	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I am motivated to actively participate in school programs.	3.44	Strongly Impacted	5.5
2. The Master Teacher’s recognition of my efforts boosts my morale.	3.40	Strongly Impacted	9
3. The Master Teacher inspires me to maintain enthusiasm for teaching.	3.46	Strongly Impacted	3
4. I am motivated to participate in professional learning communities.	3.44	Strongly Impacted	5.5
5. Master Teachers’ leadership increases my commitment to student learning.	3.42	Strongly Impacted	8
6. The Master Teacher provides feedback that enhances my motivation.	3.44	Strongly Impacted	5.5
7. I was able to establish a positive and collaborative school environment.	3.48	Strongly Impacted	2
8. There is continuous improvement in my teaching.	3.54	Strongly Impacted	1
9. The Master Teacher’s coaching helps me remain engaged despite challenges.	3.44	Strongly Impacted	5.5
10. The Master Teacher inspires passion and dedication in my professional responsibilities.	3.33	Strongly Impacted	10
	Overall Mean 3.44	Strongly Impacted	
<i>Legend: 1.00-1.74=No Impact</i>	<i>2.50-3.24= Impacted</i>		
<i>1.75-2.49=Slightly Impacted</i>	<i>3.25-4.00= Strongly Impacted</i>		

Table 3.4 summarized the impact of Master Teachers’ instructional leadership on teacher development in terms of teacher motivation and engagement, yielding an overall mean of 3.44 verbally interpreted as Strongly Impacted. This implies that Master Teachers play a substantial role in strengthening teachers’ enthusiasm, commitment, collaboration, and sustained involvement in professional and instructional activities. To begin with, the indicator “There is continuous improvement in my teaching” obtained the highest mean of 3.54 and ranked first, indicating that teachers experience a strong sense of ongoing

professional development under Master Teachers’ leadership. Conversely, “inspires passion and dedication in my professional responsibilities” (M=3.33) ranked lowest, though still strongly impacted, implying a relatively lesser effect on deep intrinsic motivation compared to other engagement-related dimensions.

Tanguay (2022), highlighted that master teachers create supportive and collaborative environments that build trust, accountability, and sustained engagement among educators. In general, the results indicated that Master Teachers’ instructional leadership strongly influences teacher motivation and engagement, particularly in sustaining continuous improvement, collaboration, and enthusiasm for teaching across various professional contexts.

Overall Implication

Table 3.5. Summary of the Impact of Master Teachers’ Instructional Leadership on Teacher Development

In terms of:	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
3.1. Teacher Performance	3.41	Strongly Impacted	3
3.2. Professional Growth	3.43	Strongly Impacted	2
3.3. Instructional Practices	3.39	Strongly Impacted	4
3.4. Teacher Motivation & Engagement	3.44	Strongly Impacted	1
Overall Mean	3.42	Strongly Impacted	

Legend: 1.00-1.74=No Impact
 1.75-2.49=Slightly Impacted
 2.50-3.24= Impacted
 3.25-4.00= Strongly Impacted

The overall assessment confirmed that Master Teachers’ instructional leadership Strongly Impacts teacher development across all domains, with a Grand Mean = 3.42. This indicates that teachers consistently perceive Master Teachers’ guidance, mentoring, coaching, and support as highly influential in improving their performance, professional growth, instructional practices, and motivation and engagement. Overall, the data suggests a strong and sustained positive influence, though the intensity of impact varies across dimensions. Across all indicators, the highest-rated impact is found in teacher motivation and engagement, particularly the statement “*There is continuous improvement in my teaching*” (Mean = 3.54, Rank 1). This highlights that Master Teachers are most effective in sustaining teachers’ sense of growth, motivation, and continuous professional development. It suggests that their leadership strongly reinforces teachers’ drive to improve and remain committed to instructional excellence. In contrast, the lowest-rated indicator, though still interpreted as Strongly Impacted, is “*influences my planning for differentiated instruction*” (Mean = 3.29, Rank 10 in instructional practices). This implies that while Master Teachers are effective in general instructional support and planning, support for more complex and individualized instructional strategies such as differentiation is comparatively less emphasized. This reflects a relative gap in deep instructional adaptation compared to other areas like planning, feedback, and motivation.

In synthesis, the findings indicated that Master Teachers’ instructional leadership is most impactful in strengthening teachers’ motivation, engagement, and professional growth, which in turn supports improvements in performance and instructional practices. However, enhancing support in advanced pedagogical strategies such as differentiation and innovation may further strengthen their overall instructional leadership impact on teacher development.

Table 4. Relationship Between Master Teachers’ Instructional Leadership and Teacher Development

Variable	rho	p-value	Interpretation
Leadership Skills and Teacher’s Performance	0.798	<.001	Significant

**Significant at the 0.05 level*

**Interpretation: 1= Perfect Correlation; 0.90-0.99=Very High Correlation; 0.70- 0.89=High Correlation; 0.50-0.69= Moderate Correlation; 0.30- 0.49= Low Correlation; 0.10-0.29= Negligible Correlation; 0= No Correlation*

Table 4.1 showed a high positive and significant relationship between Master Teachers’ instructional leadership and teacher development ($\rho = 0.798, p < .001$). This indicates that stronger instructional leadership is strongly associated with higher levels of teacher development across performance, professional growth, instructional practices, and motivation and engagement. The findings supported Instructional Leadership Theory (Hallinger & Murphy, 1985), Transformational Leadership Theory (Bass, 1985), Path-Goal Theory (House & Mitchell, 1974), and Social Learning Theory (Bandura, 1977), all of which emphasize leadership as a key driver of teacher improvement through guidance, motivation, and modeled practice.

Related studies (Tagacay et al., 2025; Quisquino, 2022; Cadacio & Albite, 2025) similarly confirm that instructional leadership significantly enhances teacher competence and development. However, Federico and Francisco (2024) found no significant relationship between instructional leadership and teacher performance, suggesting that leadership alone may not improve outcomes without strong institutional support. Similarly, Reyes and Opra (2025) reported no significant link between instructional supervision and teacher performance, indicating that supervision does not always directly translate to improved instructional or student outcomes. Overall, the results confirmed that Master Teachers’ instructional leadership plays a significant and substantial role in enhancing teacher development across all dimensions.

Qualitative Aspects

A. Experiences with Master Teachers’ Instructional Leadership Skills

The section below presents teachers’ experiences with their Master Teachers’ instructional leadership skills based on the interview data. Through thematic analysis, five key themes emerged from the responses: (1) Monitoring and Evaluation Practices of Master Teachers, (2) Curriculum Enhancement Leadership, (3) Modeling of Effective

Instructional Practices, (4) Mentorship and Coaching Practices, and (5) Personal Growth and Professional Development.

THEME 1: MONITORING AND EVALUATION PRACTICES OF MASTER TEACHERS

The findings indicated that monitoring and evaluation are not merely compliance-oriented activities but are largely developmental in nature. Master Teachers provide structured classroom observations, timely feedback, and reflective post-conference discussions that help teachers improve their instructional delivery and classroom management.

1.1. Constructive and Collaborative Monitoring Practices

Teachers consistently described monitoring not as a fault-finding or intimidating process, but as a supportive professional engagement characterized by observation, reflective dialogue, constructive feedback, and collegial interaction. These findings align Kusek and Rist (2004) who explained that monitoring provides performance information, while evaluation helps interpret results to guide improvement. This was evident in the participants' experiences, where post-observation feedback sessions became opportunities for reflection, instructional enhancement, and professional growth. This discussion is evident in the experience of the respondents as expressed below:

"...after the observation, kinausap niya ako calmly and sinabi niya na normal lang daw yun especially for beginning teachers. Then she gave practical suggestions like setting clearer classroom routines and giving shorter instructions sa activities. So parang doon ko na-feel na supportive talaga siya and hindi ka matatakot mag-improve." [KII4, L 192-196]

("...after the observation, she spoke to me calmly and said that this was normal, especially for beginning teachers. Then she gave practical suggestions like setting clearer classroom routines and giving shorter instructions for activities. So I felt like she was really supportive and that you shouldn't be afraid to improve." [KII4, L 192-196])

"My experience with monitoring is characterized by constructive oversight. Rather than a high-stakes inspection, the Master Teacher's presence in the classroom feels like a collaborative audit of student engagement." [KII9, L 517-519]

"Ang experience ko rito ay non-intrusive at relaxed. Binibigyan ako ng MT ko ng sapat na space para i-manage ang klase ko. Kapag may monitoring, hindi siya 'yung tipong nakabantay sa bawat galaw; mas focus siya sa pag-provide ng supportive feedback kaysa sa paghahanap ng mali. Nararamdaman kong pinagkakatiwalaan niya ang kakayahan ko bilang guro." [KII8, L 467-471]

("My experience here is non-intrusive and relaxed. My MT gives me enough space to manage my class. When monitoring, she is not the type to watch every move; she focuses more on providing supportive feedback than finding faults. I feel like she trusts my abilities as a teacher). [KII8, L 467-471]

1.2. Continuous Tracking of Teaching Needs and Instructional Gaps

This sub-theme reflects how Master Teachers consistently monitor and identify specific teaching needs and instructional gaps to guide improvement in classroom practice. Rather than focusing solely on overall performance, their evaluation centers on pinpointing areas that require adjustment in pedagogy, pacing, learner engagement, and alignment with instructional standards. This allows teachers to receive targeted feedback that directly informs their instructional refinement. Instructional supervision literature underscores that monitoring is not limited to observation but includes identifying instructional gaps and providing targeted interventions to improve teaching effectiveness (Hare, 2017). This is evident in the experiences of the following respondents:

“I still remember one classroom observation where she pointed out that my discussion was informative, but my pacing was too fast for some learners.” [KII3, L 112-113]

“...After the class, calmly, sinabi niya muna yung strengths ko like malinaw daw yung explanation ko sa lesson. Tapos saka niya sinabi yung kailangan kong improve, especially sa pacing and classroom management.” [KII4, L 199-202]

“After the class, calmly, he first mentioned my strengths, like how clear my explanation was in the lesson. Then he said what I needed to improve on, especially in pacing and classroom management.” [KII4, L 199-202]

“During post-observation conferences, the dialogue focuses on instructional gaps, where the Master Teacher uses my classroom data to suggest specific refinements in my teaching-learning process.” [KII9, L 519-521]

THEME 2: CURRICULUM ENHANCEMENT LEADERSHIP

This theme also emphasizes that curriculum enhancement is not a one-time task but a continuous process involving collaboration, supervision, and instructional refinement. Across the participants, curriculum enhancement was consistently described as a structured yet supportive process where Master Teachers provide guidance in lesson planning, instructional design, and the adaptation of teaching strategies. Although approaches vary from strict compliance monitoring to more flexible and developmental support, the overall experience reflects a strong emphasis on coherence, alignment, and continuous improvement of instructional practices. This theme was elaborated through sub-themes as presented below.

2.1. Master Teachers as Guides in Curriculum Alignment and Standards Integration

Curriculum alignment is experienced by teachers as a structured and intentional process where lesson objectives, learning activities, and assessments are continuously checked and refined to ensure coherence with established educational expectations. Through this process, Master Teachers serve as instructional guides who emphasize standards-based teaching while also promoting learner-centered practices. This finding aligns with Ma and Marion (2021), who described curriculum enhancement as a

continuous process aimed at improving instructional outcomes through alignment with educational standards and learner needs. The teachers' experiences reflect this ongoing refinement of instruction guided by structured standards as expressed below:

"Ah... whenever we prepared lesson plans, she constantly reminded us to check whether our objectives, activities, and assessments were aligned with the curriculum standards and PPST competencies. She would sometimes review our work and ask questions that made us rethink our lesson structure." [K113, L 118-121]

"From what I experienced, she constantly reminded us to connect everything in the lesson to the competencies and standards. She would often ask us questions like, 'What specific competency are you trying to develop through this activity?' [K115, L 306-308]

"Ang MT ko ay nagsisilbing expert guide. Kabalo gyod siya sa in-and-out sa curriculum. Ginatabangan ko niya sa pag-align sa akong lessons sa PPST competencies sa paagi nga dili forced." [K117, L 425-427]

("My MT serves as an expert guide. He really knows the ins and outs of the curriculum. He helps me align my lessons with the PPST competencies in a way that is not forced." [K117, L 425-427])

2.2. Master Teachers as Facilitators of Curriculum Localization and Instructional Adaptation

Teachers' narratives revealed that Master Teachers play a facilitative role in curriculum localization and instructional adaptation by guiding, mentoring, and enabling teachers to make instruction more relevant, responsive, and aligned with both standards and learners' contextual needs. Local studies cited by Cadacio and Albite (2024), particularly Reyes and De Guzman (2023), Santos and Alvarez (2024), and Mendoza and Salazar (2022), emphasize the important role of Master Teachers in curriculum contextualization and the development of culturally relevant instructional materials, especially in resource-limited settings. These practices are evident in the teachers' narratives, as reflected below:

"The Master Teacher serves as a curricular anchor. They assist in the localization and indigenization of lessons, ensuring that the MELCs are not just met but are aligned with the PPST. They help bridge the gap between theoretical standards and the practical realities of our HUMSS students' needs." [K119, L 522-525]

"May time nga na yung lesson ko puro discussion lang talaga. Tapos sinabi niya na under PPST, kailangan mas learner centered yung approach. So she suggested na mag-add ako ng collaborative activities and reflective questions para mas active yung students. Tapos she explained din kung anong PPST indicators yung na-aapply namin sa classroom practices namin." [K114, L 207-211]

“There was a time when my lesson was just discussion. Then she said that under PPST, the approach needed to be more learner-centered. So she suggested that I add collaborative activities and reflective questions so that the students would be more active. Then she also explained which PPST indicators we were applying in our classroom practices.” [KII4, L 207-211]

“Dahil hands-off siya, nagkakaroon ako ng kalayaan na i-localize at i-adapt ang curriculum base sa kung ano ang tingin kong mas epektibo para sa aking mga estudyante.” [KII8, L 474-476]

“Because he is hands-off, I have the freedom to localize and adapt the curriculum based on what I think will be most effective for my students.” [KII8, L 474-476]

THEME 3: MODELING OF EFFECTIVE INSTRUCTIONAL PRACTICES

The findings indicated that Master Teachers influence teachers not only through supervision and guidance but also through demonstration and example. Participants described how Master Teachers model effective classroom management, learner-centered instruction, assessment strategies, technology integration, and professional behavior that teachers can directly observe, adapt, and apply in their own classrooms. Despite differences in leadership styles, participants consistently viewed modeling as an influential mechanism for professional learning and instructional improvement.

3.1. Demonstration of Effective Teaching and Classroom Management

The findings revealed that Master Teachers modeled effective teaching and classroom management through calm leadership, organized instructional delivery, and positive learner engagement. Participants described how their Master Teachers demonstrated composure, authority, and balance in managing classrooms, which served as practical examples that teachers could emulate in their own instructional practice. These modeling behaviors helped teachers understand that effective classroom management is not solely based on strict discipline, but also on maintaining respectful relationships and creating a conducive learning environment. The findings supported the idea of Ojale (2019) that master teachers are regarded as models of professional and instructional competence whose expertise enables them to demonstrate exemplary teaching practices. This was reflected on the following accounts:

“What really stood out to me was her consistency in handling the class. Even when situations became stressful, she remained calm and composed.” [KII5, L 313-314]

“Nagmo-model siya sa pamamagitan ng disciplined routine. Kapag siya ang nagtuturo, makikita mo 'yung command niya sa classroom. Ipinapakita niya na ang effective teaching ay nagsisimula sa maayos na sistema mula sa pagpasok ng bata hanggang sa pag-exit.” [KII6, L 386-389]

“He models disciplined routines. When he teaches, you can see his command in the classroom. He shows that effective teaching begins with a well-organized system from the moment a child enters to the moment they exit.” [KII6, L 386-389]

“She provides a standard of excellence. Kapag nag-model siya ng lesson, makikita mo ang perfect balance ng classroom management at student engagement. Ipinapakita niya kung paano maging tech-savvy at creative habang sinusunod ang DepEd standards.” [KII7, L 429-431]

(“She provides a standard of excellence. When she models a lesson, you can see the perfect balance of classroom management and student engagement. She shows how to be tech-savvy and creative while adhering to DepEd standards.” [KII7, L 429-431])

3.2 Modeling Instructional Design, Assessment, and Differentiation

This sub-theme emphasizes how Master Teachers modeled effective instructional design by guiding teachers in aligning learning activities, assessment strategies, and differentiated instruction with meaningful learning outcomes. Participants expressed that their Master Teachers demonstrated how instructional decisions should be purposeful, learner-centered, and responsive to students’ diverse needs. Through modeling and instructional guidance, teachers became more aware of the importance of reflective questioning, collaborative learning, and effective assessment practices in improving classroom instruction. This was manifested in the following statements:

“...it helped me understand that alignment is not only about compliance but about ensuring meaningful learning for the students.” [KII3, L 124-125]

“So she suggested na mag-add ako ng collaborative activities and reflective questions para mas active yung students.” [KII4, L 208-210]

(“So she suggested that I add collaborative activities and reflective questions so that the students would be more active.” [KII4, L 208-210])

“She suggested that I ask more open-ended questions and include activities that would encourage participation from quieter learners.” [KII5, 301-302]

These responses indicated that Master Teachers modeled instructional approaches that promote deeper learner engagement, critical thinking, and active participation in the learning process.

3.3. Modeling Professionalism, Collaboration, and Innovation

Master Teachers modeled professionalism and innovation by encouraging teachers to integrate technology, explore innovative teaching approaches, and continuously improve their instructional competencies. Participants described how their Master Teachers influenced them to become more creative, adaptive, and technologically capable in responding to the evolving demands of teaching and learning. This modeling of innovation allowed teachers to expand their instructional strategies and develop confidence in using digital tools in the classroom. This was manifested in the following accounts:

“...she introduced us to online tools and interactive activities. Naalala ko first time kong gumamit ng quiz app sa class, sobrang kabado ako kasi baka hindi

mag-work. Pero naging excited yung students and mas active sila during the discussion.” [K114, L 261-264]

“Ang pagiging ideal niya ang nag-push sa akin na maging Microsoft expert at maging mas aktibo sa mga school initiatives.” [K117, L 446-448]

“His idealism pushed me to become a Microsoft expert and be more active in school initiatives.” [K117, L 446-448]

“The most significant influence is the diversification of my instructional toolkit. The Master Teacher’s emphasis on technology integration and innovative assessment has pushed me to move away from traditional methods, allowing me to better adapt to the diverse learning styles and linguistic backgrounds of my students.” [K119, L 547-550]

THEME 4: MENTORSHIP AND COACHING PRACTICES OF MASTER TEACHERS

Mentorship is characterized as a blend of supportive guidance, structured coaching, and reflective professional dialogue that helps teachers improve their instructional competence and confidence. Master Teachers do not only provide technical assistance but also foster a professional relationship grounded on trust, openness, and continuous improvement. Participants consistently described mentorship as both developmental and practical, where coaching is tailored to individual teacher needs and grounded in real classroom experiences.

4.1. Trust-Based Coaching and Reflective Dialogue

The findings revealed that mentorship and coaching among Master Teachers are grounded in trust, openness, and reflective professional dialogue. Participants described coaching experiences as supportive interactions where teachers are given space to think, reflect, and develop their own instructional decisions. Rather than immediately providing directives, Master Teachers establish a safe and respectful environment that encourages honest communication and professional reflection. These findings align with Acera (2024), who emphasized that mentorship is a professional relationship grounded in trust and support, aimed at facilitating teacher learning and development. Below are the statements of the respondents to support the claims above:

“She would not always give direct answers immediately. Instead, she allowed us to process things on our own.” [K113, L 103-105]

“Well... she was the type of mentor who really listened first before giving advice.” [K115, L 321]

“...the Master Teacher....provides a safe space for professional trial and error, moving me from a state of guided practice to professional autonomy.” [K119, L 531-534]

4.2 Targeted Individualized Coaching and Professional Scaffolding

Most respondents expressed that their Master Teachers provide individualized coaching that addresses the specific instructional needs and professional concerns of teachers. Coaching practices were described as practical, focused, and responsive, allowing teachers to receive direct guidance and targeted strategies for improving their classroom instruction and professional performance. Through one-on-one mentoring and post-conference discussions, teachers were guided in identifying weaknesses, refining instructional practices, and developing confidence in handling classroom challenges. Hare (2024) emphasized that master teachers play a vital role in mentoring teachers who experience instructional difficulties by providing technical assistance and targeted guidance.

“Our Master Teacher provides personalized coaching by addressing my specific needs. He conducts one-on-one mentoring sessions where we discuss my challenges, set professional goals, and monitor my progress.” [KII3, L 64-66]

“After my classroom observation, we had a one-on-one post-conference where she discussed my strengths and areas for improvement. She is approachable and provides suggestions on how I can better align my lessons with curriculum standards and PPST competencies.” [KII10, L 556-569]

4.3. Resource Sharing and Capacity Building

Master Teachers actively support teachers' professional capacity building through resource provision and instructional materials. Participants emphasized that mentorship extends beyond feedback and coaching, as Master Teachers also provide practical materials, templates, and opportunities that enhance instructional preparation and long-term career development. This form of support enables teachers to access relevant tools that improve lesson planning, teaching efficiency, and instructional quality. This was reflected in the following statements:

“Malaking tulong din yung pagbibigay niya ng sample lesson plans, teaching materials, and practical advice based on her own experience.” [KII4, L 286-287] (“She also provided sample lesson plans, teaching materials, and practical advice based on her own experience, which was a big help.” [KII4, L 286-287])

“Inihahanda niya ang mga materyales at resources bago ko pa man ito hingin, kaya laging enriched ang aking mga lesson plans.” [KII7, L 427-428]

“He prepares materials and resources before I even ask for them, so my lesson plans are always “enriched.” [KII7, L 427-428]

“The provision of instructional templates and best practice materials has been vital in reducing my administrative load.” [KII9, L 559-560]

THEME 5: PERSONAL GROWTH AND PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT

Master Teachers significantly contribute to the personal and professional growth of teachers by fostering continuous learning, reflective practice, and leadership development. Overall, their influence extends beyond instructional supervision, as they serve as catalysts for teachers' career advancement, self-improvement, and engagement in broader professional opportunities.

5.1. Engagement in Professional Learning and Collaboration

Master Teachers promote teachers' personal and professional growth by actively encouraging engagement in professional learning opportunities and collaborative practices. Participants described how they were motivated to participate in workshops, professional learning communities, and collaborative partnerships that strengthened their instructional competencies and broadened their professional perspectives. This indicates that professional growth is fostered through continuous exposure to shared learning experiences and collegial engagement. These are supported by Cadacio and Albite (2024), who emphasized that professional development and collaborative learning are essential in strengthening instructional leadership capacity and teacher effectiveness.

“There were times when I hesitated to join seminars or trainings because I thought I was already too busy, but she encouraged me to see those opportunities as investments for my future. Because of her mindset and encouragement, I gradually became more interested in attending workshops and improving my skills.” [KII5, L 330-333]

“The Master Teacher acts as a catalyst for advancement. They do not merely suggest workshops; they align professional development opportunities with my career goals in school administration. Their role is to transform mandatory attendance into a purposeful pursuit of expertise.” [KII9, L 535-538]

“There were times when I felt tired or hesitant about attending trainings because of workloads, but her words encouraged me to continue participating and learning. She always reminded us that every opportunity contributes to our future development.” [KII3, L 141-144]

5.2. Leadership Development and Career Advancement

Participants described how their Master Teachers gradually expanded their roles beyond classroom instruction by encouraging active participation in school-based initiatives and promoting higher professional qualifications. This exposure allowed teachers to develop leadership skills, organizational awareness, and readiness for future higher positions in the educational system. Similarly, UNESCO (2014) highlighted that Master Teachers are not only instructional coaches but also facilitators of broader professional roles, including participation in curriculum development, training programs, and school-wide initiatives that nurture leadership skills. This was evident in the statements of the respondents:

“Pero yung Master Teacher namin, lagi niya akong ine-encourage na mag-volunteer and mag-take ng responsibilities. One time, she encouraged me to help sa reading program ng school.” [KII4, L 254-256]

“But our Master Teacher, she always encouraged me to volunteer and take on responsibilities. One time, she encouraged me to help with the school's reading program.” [KII4, L 254-256]

“But she encouraged me to try, even if I felt unprepared at first. Because of her support, I gained more confidence in participating in committees and school improvement activities. I also became more open to opportunities for professional growth.” [KII5, L 349-352]

5.3 Reflective Practice and Continuous Improvement

Participants expressed how their engagement with Master Teachers encouraged them to critically evaluate their instructional decisions, refine their teaching strategies, and adopt a more intentional and data-informed approach to teaching. This reflective orientation strengthened their sense of professionalism and supported continuous improvement in classroom practice.

“This guidance has helped me become more reflective and confident in my teaching.” [KII3, L 66-67]

“I learned to evaluate my own strategies first and think about what adjustments I could make.” [KII5, L 339-340]

“Malaki ang naging influence niya sa professionalism ko. Dahil alam kong strict siya, naging perfectionist na rin ako sa lesson planning at classroom management. Nabawasan 'yung pagiging kampante ko; naging mas organized at systematic ako salamat ng deliverables ko para laging ready for inspection.” [KII6, L 400-403]

“He had a huge influence on my professionalism. Because I knew he was strict, I also became a perfectionist in lesson planning and classroom management. I became less complacent; I became more organized and systematic in all my deliverables so that I was always ready for inspection.” [KII6, L 400-403]

B. Impact of Master Teachers' Instructional Leadership on Teacher Development

The section below presents impact of Master Teachers' instructional leadership skills on teacher development based on the interview data. Through thematic analysis, four key themes emerged from the responses: (1) Influence on Teacher Performance, (2) Influence on Professional Growth, (3) Influence on Instructional Practices, and (4) Influence on Teacher Motivation and Engagement.

THEME 1. INFLUENCE ON TEACHER PERFORMANCE & INSTRUCTIONAL PRACTICES

Participants described how the guidance, feedback, and coaching provided by Master Teachers contributed to noticeable improvements in their instructional delivery, classroom management, and alignment with professional standards. Rather than being viewed as external supervision, the influence of Master Teachers was experienced as developmental support that strengthened teachers' effectiveness in the classroom. This theme is categorized into sub-themes supported by statements from the respondents to further explain the findings.

1.1. Enhancement of Instructional Effectiveness and Delivery

Participants described notable improvements in their ability to organize lessons, plan instruction more efficiently, and deliver teaching in a more structured and coherent manner. This indicated that Master Teachers contribute not only to compliance with instructional requirements but also to the refinement of day-to-day teaching practices that directly affect classroom effectiveness. The results align with Tagacay et al. (2025), who emphasized that Master Teachers significantly contribute to improving teacher performance through coaching, mentoring, and instructional support, particularly in lesson planning and classroom delivery.

"Well... compared before, I became more organized and confident because of her guidance. Lesson planning became easier for me since she taught us how to focus on the essential parts of instruction instead of overcomplicating everything." [K113, L 151-153]

"Sa lesson planning po, mas naging organized ako because of her guidance. Before kasi, minsan overloaded yung activities ko and hindi ko natatapos lahat within the period." [K114, L 246-247]

"In lesson planning, I became more organized because of her guidance. Before, sometimes my activities were overloaded and I couldn't finish everything within the period." [K114, 246-247]

"Because of those lessons, my teaching became more organized and effective." [K115, L 346]

"Through their guidance, my lesson planning has become more data-driven and my classroom management more proactive. This systematic approach has directly resulted in more organized instructional flow and improved learner outcomes." [K119, L 539-542]

1.2 Strengthened Classroom Management and Learning Outcomes

Participants emphasized observable improvements in learner behavior, engagement, discipline, and the overall classroom climate because of continuous guidance, feedback, and coaching provided by Master Teachers. This indicated that

instructional leadership extends beyond lesson planning and delivery, shaping how teachers establish routines, manage student behavior, and sustain a productive learning environment. The findings are supported by Hallinger (2011), who emphasized that instructional leadership contributes to school effectiveness by strengthening classroom processes and fostering positive learning environments. This was highlighted in the following statements:

“She even suggested na gumamit ako ng energizer before group activities para bumalik yung focus ng students. Tinry ko siya the following week and honestly, nakita ko naman na naging mas cooperative yung class.” [KII4, L 203-205]

“She even suggested that I use an energizer before group activities to get the students' focus back. I tried it the following week and honestly, I saw that the class became more cooperative.” [KII4, L 203-205]

“Seeing those techniques firsthand helped me understand that effective classroom management is not about being strict all the time, but about creating a positive and organized learning environment”. [KII5, 318-320]

“This systematic approach has directly resulted in more organized instructional flow and improved learner outcomes.” [KII9, L 541-542]

“I have learned various classroom management techniques, such as establishing routines, using positive discipline, and maintaining an engaging learning environment.” [KII1, L 14-16]

1.3 Standards Alignment and Assessment Accuracy

The findings revealed that Master Teachers' instructional leadership significantly influences teachers' ability to align instruction with educational standards and improve the accuracy of assessment practices. Participants elaborate how continuous guidance from Master Teachers helped them ensure that lessons, activities, and assessments were consistently anchored on curriculum competencies and professional teaching standards. This reflects a strong emphasis on standards-based instruction and accountability in teaching practice.

“I can say that she had a huge influence on my development as a teacher. Through her guidance, I learned to value substance more than appearance when it comes to teaching.” [KII3, L 145-147]

“Because of her guidance, I became more careful in planning lessons and more aware of the importance of aligning instruction with the curriculum and PPST indicators.” [KII5, L 310-312]

“Sa kanya ko natutunan ang art of compliance sa COT. Dahil sa guidance niya, alam ko na kung paano i-hit 'yung mga indicators na kailangan sa rubric, mula sa ICT integration hanggang sa pag-address ng student diversity. Naging mas intentional ako sa pagpili ng strategies na siguradong gagana at papasa sa standard.” [KII6, L 408-411]

“From him I learned the art of compliance in COT. Because of his guidance, I now know how to hit the indicators required in the rubric, from ICT integration to addressing student diversity. I have become more intentional in choosing strategies that will definitely work and pass the standard.” [K116, L 408-411]

THEME 2. INFLUENCE ON PROFESSIONAL GROWTH

Master Teachers played a key role in shaping their career development, strengthening their professional competencies, and motivating them to pursue continuous improvement. This influence was not limited to instructional support but extended to broader professional development, including participation in training, engagement in school initiatives, and pursuit of higher qualifications. As a result, teachers developed a stronger sense of direction in their careers and became more proactive in seeking growth opportunities within and beyond their schools.

2.1 Career Development and Advancement

The findings revealed how Master Teachers provided direction and motivation that helped teachers envision long-term career goals, including graduate studies and potential administrative positions. This reflects the role of instructional leadership in shaping not only classroom practice but also broader professional trajectories. This was evident in the statements of the following respondents:

“Her advice to pursue graduate studies motivated me to consider long-term career development.” [K110, L 589-590]

“I used to avoid leadership roles or participation in school programs because I was afraid of making mistakes. But she encouraged me to try, even if I felt unprepared at first. Because of her support, I gained more confidence in participating in committees and school improvement activities. I also became more open to opportunities for professional growth.” [K115, L 348-352]

“Palagi niya akong gina-encourage na mag-enroll sa graduate studies o kumuha ng certifications. Hindi niya ako pinipilit dahil sa compliance, kundi dahil gusto niyang makita akong mag-succeed sa aking career. She genuinely cares about my professional advancement.” [K117, L 438-441]

“She always encourages me to enroll in graduate studies or get certifications. She doesn’t pressure me out of compliance, but because she wants to see me succeed in my career. She genuinely cares about my professional advancement.” [K117, L 438-441]

2.2. Skill Enhancement and Innovation

Instructional guidance and professional support from Master Teachers as expressed by the respondents, enabled them to become more flexible, creative, and confident in their teaching practices. This reflects a shift from traditional instruction toward more adaptive and innovative approaches that respond to diverse learner needs. As mentioned by Quisquino (2022), exposure to varied instructional strategies and methodologies facilitated by Master Teachers contributes significantly to teacher

professional growth and improved teaching effectiveness. This highlights that Master Teachers play a crucial role in equipping teachers with the skills necessary to adapt to evolving educational demands. This was explained by the respondents:

“Because of her guidance, I started exploring more interactive activities, alternative assessments, and technology-based resources.” [K118, L 355-357]

“The most significant influence is the diversification of my instructional toolkit. The Master Teacher’s emphasis on technology integration and innovative assessment has pushed me to move away from traditional methods, allowing me to better adapt to the diverse learning styles and linguistic backgrounds of my students.” [K119, L 547-550]

THEME 3: INFLUENCE ON TEACHER MOTIVATION & ENGAGEMENT

The findings highlight how Master Teachers play an important role in sustaining teachers’ enthusiasm, commitment, and active participation in both classroom and school-related activities. Their leadership fosters a supportive and encouraging environment where teachers feel valued, trusted, and motivated to continuously improve their practice. Participants consistently described how feedback, recognition, guidance, and professional trust from Master Teachers contributed to their increased motivation and sustained engagement in teaching.

3.1. Intrinsic Motivation and Commitment to Teaching

Data revealed how continuous guidance, support, and professional trust from Master Teachers contributed to a deeper sense of purpose, discipline, and inspiration in their work. This suggests that motivation is not only externally driven but also internally developed through reflective practice and meaningful instructional experiences. Based on the following accounts:

“As time went by, I realized that her approach was intentional because she wanted us to strengthen our critical and analytical thinking. Looking at it now, I can say that her way of mentoring helped me become more observant and thoughtful in handling situations inside the classroom” [K113, L 105-108]

“She always encouraged us to go beyond compliance and really think about the quality of learning we provide to students. Because of that, I became more disciplined and intentional in my teaching.” [K115, L 294-296]

“She is a source of inspiration. Ang pagiging ideal na lider niya ang dahilan kung bakit mataas ang aking morale.” [K117, L 454-455]

“She is a source of inspiration. Her being an ideal leader is the reason why my morale is high.” [K117, L 454-455]

3.2. Engagement in School Activities

The findings revealed that Master Teachers' instructional leadership encourages teachers' active engagement in school and professional activities. Participants described how opportunities and support provided by Master Teachers influenced their participation in school programs and broader institutional initiatives. This suggested that engagement is strengthened when teachers are given both direction and professional trust in fulfilling their roles within the school community. The findings are supported by Oliva and Bautista (2025), who emphasized that instructional leadership strengthens collaboration among teachers and enhances their engagement in instructional and institutional processes. This suggests that participation increases when teachers operate within a supportive and collaborative professional environment. This was reflected in the following statements:

"She influenced my participation in school programs, LAC sessions, and other initiatives. Her mentorship has inspired me to take on responsibilities that contribute to school improvement and to aim for career advancement." [KII1, L 28-30]

"Dahil doon, mas naging engaged ako sa mga school activities kasi ayaw kong mapahiya sa standard na itinanim niya sa amin." [KII6, L 414-415]

"Because of that, I became more engaged in school activities because I didn't want to be embarrassed by the standards he instilled in us." [KII6, L 414-415]

"Ang kanyang professional temperament ang nagsisilbing ehemplo ko sa kung paano dapat i-handle ang mga tao at sitwasyon sa school nang walang stress." [KII8, L 479-481]

"His professional temperament serves as my example of how to handle people and situations at school without stress." [KII8, 479-481]

C. Challenges and supports that shape teachers' development under Master Teachers' leadership

THEME 1: CHALLENGES THAT SHAPE TEACHERS' DEVELOPMENT UNDER MASTER TEACHERS' LEADERSHIP

The challenges encountered by teachers were associated with workload demands, diverse learner needs, limited resources, pressure from evaluation standards, and varying levels of instructional support. These findings suggests that teacher development under Master Teachers' leadership is shaped not only by guidance and mentorship but also by contextual and institutional realities that influence teachers' ability to implement instructional improvements effectively.

1.1. Time Constraints and Workload Pressure

Teachers explained that implementing innovative teaching strategies and preparing enhanced lesson plans required additional preparation time, which became

difficult alongside paperwork, coaching responsibilities, and school-related assignments. This finding indicates that workload demands significantly affect teachers' ability to maximize the instructional guidance provided by Master Teachers. Although teachers recognized the value of innovative and learner-centered practices, limited time often restricted full implementation.

“Some challenges I have encountered include time constraints in preparing enhanced lesson plans, difficulty in applying new teaching strategies immediately, and limited resources for implementing innovative approaches.” [KII1, L 37-39]

“Another challenge was time management. Implementing new teaching strategies often required additional preparation, and balancing that with paperwork and other responsibilities sometimes became difficult.” [KII5, L 367-369]

“The primary challenge is the time-poverty created by the heavy demands of teaching, coaching, and administrative paperwork, which often slows the full implementation of new strategies. Translating high-level pedagogical theories into a classroom with limited technological resources often requires significant improvisation.” [KII9, L 555-558]

1.2 Adaptation and Contextual Difficulties

The findings also showed that teachers struggle with adapting instructional strategies to varying classroom contexts. While Master Teachers provide guidance, not all strategies are easily transferable to different learner needs and classroom conditions. This was reflected in the statements of the following respondents:

“One challenge for me was the actual implementation of the strategies she suggested. I realized that not all strategies work the same way in every classroom setting because learners have different needs and personalities.” [KII3, L 175-177]

“I think one of the main challenges was adapting the strategies to different classroom situations. Some approaches worked effectively in one section but not in another because learners responded differently.” [KII5, L 365-377]

1.3. Resource and Technology Limitations

Teachers reported difficulties in implementing technology-integrated and innovative teaching strategies because of unstable internet connections, limited gadgets, and insufficient classroom resources. The findings imply that resource limitations significantly constrain teachers' capacity to apply modern instructional approaches encouraged by Master Teachers. As shared by the respondents:

Another challenge din is technology integration. Minsan unstable yung internet or hindi lahat ng students may gadgets, so hindi laging effective yung planned activities. [KII4, L 276-278]

(Another challenge is technology integration. Sometimes the internet is unstable or not all students have gadgets, so planned activities are not always effective. [KII4, L 276-278])

“Some challenges I have encountered include....and limited resources for implementing innovative approaches.” [KII1, L 37-39]

“...Translating high-level pedagogical theories into a classroom with limited technological resources often requires significant improvisation.” [KII9, L 557-558]

1.4. Pressure from Standards and Evaluation

Some participants described experiencing pressure and anxiety due to strict supervision, classroom observation standards, and high expectations from Master Teachers. Teachers explained that fear of committing mistakes during observations sometimes affected instructional confidence and spontaneity. The findings suggests that while standards-based supervision promotes accountability and professionalism, excessive pressure may also create anxiety that affects authentic teaching performance.

“Pinakamalaking challenge ’yung kaba tuwing may observation. Minsan kasi, dahil sa takot na magkamali sa rules, nagiging mechanical o stiff ’yung pagtuturo imbes na natural. Mahirap mag-adjust on the spot kapag may unexpected na nangyari sa klase, kasi iniisip ko agad kung papayagan ba ito ng MT ko o bawal ba ito sa rubric.” [KII6, L 416-419]

“The biggest challenge is the nervousness during observations. Sometimes, because of the fear of breaking the rules, teaching becomes mechanical or stiff instead of natural. It’s hard to adjust on the spot when something unexpected happens in class, because I immediately wonder if my MT will allow it or if it’s not allowed in the rubric.” [KII6, L 416-419]

“Usahay, tungod kay ideal siya, ang challenge nako kay ang pag-reach sa high level of excellence nga iyang gina-set.” [KII7, L 458-459]

“Sometimes, because he is ideal, my challenge is to reach the high level of excellence that he sets.” [KII7, L 458-459]

THEME 2: SUPPORTS THAT SHAPE TEACHERS’ DEVELOPMENT UNDER MASTER TEACHERS’ LEADERSHIP

In contrast to the challenges identified, the findings also revealed strong forms of support provided by Master Teachers that significantly aid teacher development. Overall, these supports are characterized by continuous mentoring, emotional encouragement, and structured instructional assistance. These systems help teachers navigate challenges, build confidence, and improve instructional competence. To further understand this concept, it was categorized into sub-themes supported by statements from the respondents.

2.1. Mentoring, Feedback, and Coaching Support Systems

The findings revealed that Master Teachers provide consistent mentoring and coaching support that allows teachers to learn through guided practice and reflection.

This supportive structure enables teachers to view mistakes as learning opportunities and gradually improve their instructional practices.

“For me, one of the most meaningful supports she gave was allowing me to experience mistakes and learn from them. She did not expect perfection immediately, which made me feel less pressured and more willing to improve. [KII3, L 181-183]

“For me, the most helpful support was her encouragement and understanding. Whenever I encountered difficulties, she did not immediately criticize my shortcomings. Instead, she guided me patiently and gave practical suggestions that I could actually apply.” [KII5, L 371-374]

“The provision of instructional templates and best practice materials has been vital in reducing my administrative load. The most helpful support is the culture of openness knowing that I can approach my Master Teacher with a failure and receive a solution rather than a reprimand. This safety net is the foundation of my development.” [KII9, L 559-562]

2.2 Emotional and Professional Encouragement

The findings also highlighted the emotional dimension of instructional leadership, where Master Teachers provide encouragement that builds teachers' confidence and reduces fear of failure. These responses suggest that emotional safety plays a crucial role in sustaining positive and trusting professional environment.

“...her encouragement gave me confidence to take risks and trust my capabilities. Because of that, I became more willing to improve my professional skills and become involved in different school activities.” [KII3, L 159-161]

“Ang pinakamalaking support ay ang absence of fear. Dahil alam kong mabait siya, mas malakas ang loob kong aminin ang aking mga kahinaan at humingi ng tulong nang walang halong kaba. Ang pagbibigay niya sa akin ng laya ang pinaka-supportive na act niya. It makes me feel empowered and trusted, na siyang pinaka-importanteng factor sa development ko bilang isang lisensyadong guro.” [KII8, L 512-516]

“The biggest support is the absence of fear. Because I know he is kind, I feel more confident to admit my weaknesses and ask for help without any nervousness. His giving me freedom is his most supportive act. It makes me feel empowered and trusted, which is the most important factor in my development as a licensed teacher.” [KII8, 512-516]

“I also appreciated that she trusted us enough to learn from our own experiences. She allowed us to make mistakes, reflect on them, and improve step by step. Because of that support, I became more confident and resilient as a teacher.” [KII5, 371-376]

2.3 Structural and Resource-Based Support

The findings further revealed that Master Teachers provide tangible instructional support through materials, templates, and collaborative structures. These resources help teachers improve lesson preparation and instructional delivery efficiency. This was reflected in the following statements:

“Malaking tulong din yung pagbibigay niya ng sample lesson plans, teaching materials, and practical advice based on her own experience.” [KII4, L 286-287].

“Her provision of sample lesson plans, teaching materials, and practical advice based on her own experience was also a great help.” [KII4, L 286-287].

“The provision of instructional templates and best practice materials has been vital in reducing my administrative load.” [KII9, L 559-560]

“The most helpful support from my Master Teacher includes post-observation feedback and collaborative meetings, which provided direction for improvement.” [KII10, 610-611]

Integration of Findings

The integration of quantitative and qualitative findings reveals both convergence and complementarity in how Master Teachers' instructional leadership influences teacher development. The narratives consistently showed that Master Teachers are most effective in relational and facilitative leadership roles, particularly through mentoring, coaching, and monitoring practices that emphasize reflective dialogue, individualized feedback, and continuous professional support. Teachers described monitoring and evaluation as constructive and collaborative, where feedback was developmental rather than punitive, allowing them to refine instructional practices through guided reflection. This explains why monitoring and evaluation received a high quantitative rating. Similarly, mentorship and coaching emerged as the strongest leadership dimension both quantitatively and qualitatively. Teachers consistently highlighted trust-based coaching, individualized support, and professional scaffolding, which fostered confidence, competence, and autonomy. This aligns with the highest impact on teacher motivation and engagement, where qualitative data showed that encouragement, trust, and emotional support significantly strengthened teachers' commitment, enthusiasm, and sustained participation in school activities.

The qualitative findings also help explain the moderate results in areas related to adaptability, innovation, and responsiveness to emerging instructional trends. While some Master Teachers integrate technology and innovative strategies, these practices are not uniformly experienced across participants. This variation suggested that instructional innovation is present but not yet fully institutionalized within Master Teachers' leadership practices.

Conclusions

Quantitative results confirmed a significant positive relationship between instructional leadership and teacher development, while qualitative findings reinforced these results by portraying Master Teachers as mentors, instructional guides, curriculum facilitators, and role models who support teachers through feedback, reflection, coaching, and collaboration. The integration of both data strands shows strong convergence, confirming that instructional leadership enhances teachers' confidence, competence, and professional engagement. However, areas such as differentiated instruction, technology integration, instructional innovation, and structured support especially for newly hired teachers require further strengthening to achieve a more balanced and comprehensive instructional leadership impact.

Recommendations

It is recommended that Master Teachers further strengthen their roles in mentorship, coaching, instructional modeling, and curriculum leadership through structured demonstration teaching, classroom observations, technology integration, and instructional innovation. School administrators and heads should provide strong institutional support by establishing structured coaching programs, allocating time and resources for mentoring activities, and promoting collaborative curriculum planning and peer learning opportunities. Future researchers may further explore instructional leadership in other contexts, examine barriers to its effective implementation, and employ longitudinal or expanded mixed-method designs to assess long-term impacts on teacher and student outcomes.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors declare that this study was conducted in full compliance with ethical research standards. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents prior to their participation, and they were clearly informed of their right to voluntarily participate and withdraw from the study at any time without penalty. The anonymity and confidentiality of all respondents were strictly maintained, and data privacy protocols were observed throughout the data collection, analysis, and reporting processes to safeguard participants' information and well-being. The study posed no harm to the participants, and their welfare was prioritized at all stages of the research. The authors further declare that no conflict of interest exists in the conduct of this study, and all procedures were carried out with integrity. Plagiarism was strictly avoided, and all sources were properly acknowledged. The interpretation of findings was done objectively without bias, and the results were used solely for academic and research purposes. Full disclosure is made that artificial intelligence tools were utilized solely for language refinement and formatting support, while the intellectual content, analysis, and conclusions remain the responsibility of the authors.

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